

Stability Constant of Silver Complex with 7-Nitro-8-quinolinol-5-sulphonic Acid

M. J. MAHARAJA and I. M. BHATT*

Chemistry Department, University School of Sciences, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad-380 009

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The stability constant of a complex can be determined by various methods¹. The stability constant of silver complex cannot be determined by pH-metric technique, following well-known methods of Irving-Rossotti². This is because of the saturated KCl reference calomel electrode. It is therefore decided to study the potentiometric method employing metal electrode. The Fronaeus method³ which is most suitable for complexes having low stability constants, is attempted.

Results and Discussion

The family curves $T_L(X)T_M$ where $X = E_1 - E_2$. E_1 and E_2 are potentials of the cell,

in the absence and presence of ligand respectively. For the sake of brevity the results are not given. Vertical cuts along the family of curves at particular values of X will give corresponding solutions having the same (but unknown) values of the degree of formation \bar{n} , and free ligand concentration L , but containing different total different concentration of T_M and T_L .

On rearranging equation for degree of formation,

$$\bar{n} = T_L - L / T_M \quad (1)$$

$$\text{or, } T_L = \bar{n} T_M + L \quad (2)$$

Therefore, on plotting $T_L \rightarrow (T_M)X$ straight-line plot having slope equal to \bar{n} and intercept equal to free ligand concentration will be obtained. Only those values of X are selected that gave values of \bar{n} between 0.2 and 0.7. This appears to be more reliable.

As \bar{n} was not greater than one, the stability constant was computed taking $N = 1$; assuming that only 1 : 1 complex is formed under the experimental conditions. For $N = 1$, equation for computing stability constant is

$$\bar{n} = \frac{\beta_1 L}{1 + \beta_1 L} \quad (3)$$

Rearranging the above equation and taking logarithms, we have

$$pL = \log \beta_1 - \log \frac{\bar{n}}{1 - \bar{n}} \quad (4)$$

Value of $\log \beta_1$ was computed graphically according to equation (4). The values of pL are plotted against $\log \bar{n}/(1 - \bar{n})$ (Fig. 1) giving a straight-line with unit slope and intercept equal to $\log \beta_1$. Thus the value of $\log \beta_1$ will be 3.66. In a similar manner, $\log \beta_1$ is calculated for 20, 30, 40 and 50% dioxan-water systems. The values are found to be 3.86 4.35 4.52 and 4.60 respectively.

Effect of dielectric constant on stability constant was studied. The value of $\log \beta_1$ increased with

Fig. 1. Plot of pL vs $\log \bar{n}/(1 - \bar{n})$ of the Ag-complex.

increase in percentage of dioxan in the mixed solvent. A plot of $\log \beta_1$ against $1/D$ is a straight-line in the beginning and later as a curve. The values of the slopes for the two linear portions will give the values of minimum distance of approach or the average diameter. The values of average diameter (r) are obtained as 2.24 and 16.84 Å when dielectric constant of the medium varied from 70 to 50 and 45 to 30.

Experimental

Stock solutions of 0.01 M AgNO₃, 0.01 M Na₂R (disodium salt of NQSA) and 0.1 M NaClO₄ were prepared. AgNO₃ and Na₂R were standardised potentiometrically against standard KCl and HCl solutions respectively⁴. From the above stock solutions, different mixtures were prepared in such a way that T_M remained fixed, T_L varied from 0 to 20 mM depending upon T_M in a particular set. The total ionic strength was maintained constant at 0.01. Five series (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4 and 0.5 mM) with varying values of T_M were prepared. To each mixture, required amount of NaClO₄ was added so as to make total ionic strength as 0.01. The final volume was 50 ml. For mixed solvent system, required volumes for dioxan for 20, 30, 40 and 50% were added and diluted to 50 ml.

Two silver electrodes were prepared and its reversibility was checked from time to time during measurements. The same silver electrode, calomel electrode and salt bridge (KNO₃) were used throughout. Potential measurement was carried out at $32 \pm 0.2^\circ$ using Leeds and Northrup K4-7554 potentiometer with Cambridge spot galvanometer as a detector. The potentiometer was sensitive to ± 0.1 mV. Ionic strength greater than 0.01 M resulted in precipitation of silver-complex. In mixed solvent system, T_M more than 0.5 mM also caused the precipitation. As the stability constant of silver complex is less as compared to proton-ligand complex of NQSA ($\log K_H' = 5.72$), excess of NQSA might have to be added. This was avoided by employing disodium salt of NQSA (Na₂R).

References

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